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Sales Promotion Techniques And Consumer Purchase Intentions Of Soft Drinks In South East, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of sales promotion on customer purchase intention of selected soft drinks in South East, Nigeria. Specifically, price discount, contest and sweepstakes, coupon, bonus pack and free trail were employed as the independent variables, while customer purchase intention was used as the dependent variable. Relevant conceptual, theoretical and empirical literatures were reviewed. The study was anchored on theory of reasoned action because it is germane in explaining the effect of sales promotion and customer purchase intention. The study adopted survey research design. The population of the study consisted of consumers of nine selected soft drinks in South-East Nigeria. A sample of three hundred and eighty (384) subscribers was selected using Cochran Method of determining sample size since the population is infinite. Pilot study was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. A reliability coefficient of 0.719 was derived by the use of Cronbach Alpha coefficient. Frequency table and percentage were employed in analyzing the research questions while the hypotheses were test using regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance. This was done with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21. The study found that price discount, contest and sweepstakes, coupon, bonus pack and free trail have significant positive effect on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria. The study therefore concludes that sales promotion has significant positive effect on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria. The study recommended amongst others that producers and distributors of soft drinks in South East Nigeria should occasionally use price discount in order to stimulate sales especially during off-peak periods.

Keywords: Sales Promotion, Price Discount, Contest and Sweepstakes, Coupon, Bonus Pack, Free Trail, Customer Purchase Intention

INTRODUCTION

Consumers are faced with varieties of choices and decisions with respect to product size, quality, incentives and price (Odunlade, 2009). To retain consumers in the face of keen competition, service providers must develop marketing strategies that will not only win customers but help to retain them. Sales promotion is seen as the next available marketing strategy that help to promote sales, increase product life cycle, sales growth and enhance customers' goodwill (Oyeniyi, 2011). Sales promotion has become an effective marketing tool that assists organizations to wax stronger in a global competitive environment. Oyedapo, Akinlabi and Sufian (2012) identified sales promotion as a key ingredient in marketing campaigns which assist organization to achieve its objectives. The main aim of any business is to earn maximum profit and this is possible only through maximum sales. The maximum sales can be

achieved by using various techniques of sales promotion. It is particularly effective in spurring product trial and unplanned purchases (Aderemi, 2003).

Obasan and Soyabo (2012) argued that sales promotion plays an important role in retaining old consumers and attracting new ones. Jobber (2004) simply captures sales promotion as a package of incentives to consumers or the trade that are designed to stimulate purchase. Sales promotion plays an important role in retaining old consumers and attracting new ones. But most soft drinks firms do not employ sales promotional tools in marketing their products citing high cost involved and this have made them to lose most of their customers as new brands keeps emerging every day. This has affected the consumer purchase intention for soft drinks negatively. Furthermore, where the company invested in sales promotional activities, it is often discovered that most of the attracted consumer divert to their old products once the promotion is over making mockery of the whole essence of the promotional activities (Odunlami & Ogunsiji, 2011).

Sales promotion, a key ingredient in marketing campaigns, consists of a collection of incentive tools, mostly short term, designed to stimulate quicker or greater purchase of particular products or services by consumers of the trade (Kotler & Keller, 2009). These tools include price discount, context and sweepstakes, coupon, bonus pack and free trial. The purpose of using these sales promotional tools is to motivate the customers to immediately purchase a particular product hence enhancing its sales. Sales promotion act as a competitive weapon by providing an extra incentive for the target audience to purchase or support one brand over another. In addition, sales promotion can be an effective tool in a highly competitive market environment, when the objective is to convince retailers to carry new product or influence consumers to select it over those of competitors. Also it tends to work best when it is applied to impulse items whose features can be judged at the point of purchase, rather than more complex, expensive items that might require hands demonstration (Odunlami & Ogunsiji, 2011).

In determining the relative importance to place sales promotion in the overall marketing mix, an organization should consider its marketing budget, the stage of the product in the life cycle, the nature of competition in the market, the target of the promotion, and the nature of the product. The existence of a business is not only to produce goods and services that will be required by customers but to attract positive purchase intention. Customer purchase intention has been considered one of the most important constructs and one of the main goals in marketing. Purchase intention is a way to measure the willingness of consumers to buy a product and shows the probability that a consumer will buy a product (Devlin, Ennew, McKechnie & Smith, 2007). Purchase intentions are considered as a crucial indicator of actual purchase, as they are an awaiting transaction (Chang & Wildt, 1994). Customer purchase intentions can be defined as an individual's conscious plan to make an effort to purchase a brand. Purchase intention is an important index for evaluating consumer behavior. It represents the degree or possibility the consumer would be willing to purchase.

Purchase intention can measure the possibility of a consumer to buy a product, and the higher the purchase intention, the higher a consumer's willingness to buy a product. Consumers are more likely to have a stronger intention to purchase a product when they react favorably to sales promotion for the product (Haley & Baldinger, 2000). Purchase intention indicates to the marketers what consumer would buy. Intention is the buyer's forecast of which product they will buy. Raney, Arpan, Pashupati and Brill (2003) described purchase Intentions as a key indicator of the success of sales promotion. Persuading customers to use a particular brand is significant and could facilitate the maintenance and growth of market share of the organization. Therefore, understanding the effect of sales promotion on customer purchase intention is very important, hence the need for this research work.

Statement of Problem

Intense competition among the marketing organizations has led to the application of various marketing strategies and tactics to win a good share of the market. Sales promotion has been widely used by soft drink manufacturing firms in their attempt to outsmart their competitors. But the question now is whether sales promotion has influence on customer purchase intention. Consumers exhibit various attitudes and behavior towards the products and services offered and rendered to them. This is basically because

presently consumer's income is very low due to economic recession coupled with other environment factors that influence their buying habits. In Nigeria, it is not enough to manufacture and expect that consumer will buy the products without considering what they will benefit or drive from it. Hence, sales promotion becomes inevitable. Manufacturers are faced with the problems of products substance and competition. So for that reason many manufacturers now attempt to stimulate and get consumers attention and increase their market share by using sales promotion tools on goods and services.

Organizations usually encounter problems such as lack of management know how and not appointing the right marketers or sales promotion experts. Most sales promotions carried out by organizations are usually badly organized and implemented which leads to the aim being defeated thereby having adverse effect of organizational performance result from low sales volume and profit (Adeniran, Egwuonwu & Egwuonwu, 2016). This problem of low sales and low demand have prompted producers to use sale promotion to compliment the use of other promotional mixes like advertising, personal selling and so on. However, it has been observed that over the years, some producers do not employ the use of appropriate sales promotional tools and methods, to enhance the achievement of stated goals, and have neglected the importance of marketing concept which is people oriented philosophy that regarded the customers as a king and sole aim of the business existence.

Also, as market continues to shrink under the twin forces of a biting liquidity crunch and dropping disposable income, the scramble for local market has become so aggressive that companies need to embrace promotion strategies and rebutting the rival's payoff line, all in a desperate attempt to retain market share, fend-off competition and attract more customers. Furthermore, the empirical literature reviewed revealed conflicting findings on the effect of sales promotion on customer purchase intention. Similarly, majority of the scholarly work reviewed were foreign with only few local studies in soft drink sub-sector, hence a knowledge gap in Nigeria. Despite the previous extensive research work, there is evident gap in knowledge in terms of the effect of sales promotion on consumer purchase intention in the soft drink sub-sector in South-East, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to investigate the effect of sales promotion on customer purchase intention. Specifically, the study intends to

1. Ascertain the effect of price discount on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.
2. Determine the effect of contest and sweepstakes on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.
3. Examine the effect of coupon on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.
4. Investigate the effect of bonus pack on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.
5. Ascertain the effect of free trail on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study.

1. To what extent has price discount affect customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria?
2. To what extent do contest and sweepstakes affect customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria?
3. To what extent has coupon affect customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria?
4. To what extent does bonus pack affect customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria?
5. To what extent does free trail affect customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses stated in null form guided this study.

- Ho₁: Price discount has no significant effect on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.
- Ho₂: Contest and sweepstakes has no have significant effect on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.
- Ho₃: Coupon has no significant effect on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.
- Ho₄: Bonus pack has no significant effect on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.
- Ho₅: Free trail has no significant effect on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Sales Promotion

Sale promotion is the process of persuading the potential customers; company's communication strategy to promote an increase in sales. The sales promotion is short term tactics along with advertising, public relations and personal selling for building long term customer loyalty. Sales promotion is defined as a key ingredient in marketing campaigns, consist of a collection of incentives tools mostly short term, designed to stimulate quicker or greater purchase of particular products or service by consumers or the trade (Kotler & Keller 2011). The American Marketing Association (A.M.A 2010) defines sales promotions as "media and non –media marketing pressures applied for a predetermined time frame to different target audience, thus consumers, retailers and wholesalers in order to stimulate trial, increase consumer demand and improve product viability.

American Marketing Association (AMA) defines sales promotion as "The media and non-media marketing pressure applied for a pre-determined, limited period of time at the level of consumer, retailer, or wholesaler in order to stimulate trial, increase consumer demand, or improve product availability (American Marketing Association 2017). For AMA sales promotion is pre-determined promotion through media and non-media in order to stimulate customers to try or buy the product/service as well as increase demand or improve the availability of the product.

Oyedepo, Akinlabi and Sufian (2012) postulate that sales promotion is an uninterrupted incentive that offers an extra value or incentive for the product to the sales force, distributor, or the final consumer with main objective of creating an immediate sale. Aham (2008) notion on sales promotion is hinged on that, sales promotion was developed as the response by manufactures marketers, and marketing tactics similar to find a short term solution to the problems of surplus stock of goods which can be presented in variables manufacturer's storerooms but are not needed by customers and business. Shimp (2000) defines sales promotion as a marketing communications activities used to encourage the trade and or end customers to purchase or take other relevant action by affecting the perceived value of the product being promoted or to otherwise motivate action to be taken. Shimp's definition proposes a broader perspective to sales promotion, it permits incentivised and non-incentivised sales promotion and the opportunity for sales promotions to be undertaken by anybody.

A slightly different definition by Hackeley (2010) is of the notion that any novelty that has a brand or name bearing on it is reckoned as a sales promotion. Hackeley (2010) defines sales promotion as a vast range of novelty items that can carry promotional messages or visual representation of the brand. Often these items such as coffee mugs, pens, bags, T-shirts, the element of goodwill is bound up with the brand when they are used by the consumer. Sales promotions also refers to in-store promotions such as two-for-the- price of one, 10% off, free gifts, redeemable coupons, competition or money back for returning bottle top and self liquidating premium (Hackeley, 2010). Convectional marketing wisdom holds that the major strength of sales promotion is that they can persuade people to try the brand. It is also being argued that some brands use perpetual sales promotion.

Sales Promotional Techniques

Sales promotional strategies include consumer promotion – samples, coupons, rebates, price – offs, premiums, contests, advertising specialties, patronage rewards, point of purchase (POP) promotions, sweep stakes and games, trade promotions – buying allowances, free goods, merchandise money, dealer sales contests, sales rallies (Raghubir, Inman & Grande, 2004). Those explained below are adopted for the study

Price Discount: A price discount is the deduction of a certain amount of money from the tag prices during a certain period of time (Jin-Woo, Yu-Jin & Woo-Choon, 2013). A price discount is a very prevalent marketing strategy to attract consumers by providing an extra value or incentive, which encourages consumers to purchase the promoted products immediately (Yin & Huang, 2014). A price discount provides a monetary gain, an incentive to encourage consumers to purchase the product. In addition to economic effects of price discounts, price discounts also have informational effects, which can be defined as the effects created by the communication of direct or inferential knowledge derived from exposure to a price discount (Raghubir, Inman & Grande, 2004). A common informational route of promotion effect is quality inference.

Coupon: Coupon refers to a certificate that provides a price discount or special benefit to only the holder of that coupon (Jin-Woo, Yu-Jin & Woo-Choon, 2013). Coupons are also the frequent sales promotion techniques as discounts commonly used to motivate the customers to purchase. The coupons would push the customers to buy the product when they think that the price is high or can be incentive to buy the product above the competitors. The price sensitive customers would be willing to buy the product with availability of coupons. This price discrimination method is usually made for making the customers happy with buying or turning the customers that have experienced bad services (Raghubir, Inman & Grande, 2004).

Contest and Sweepstakes: The contests and sweepstakes are simple as winning the gifts that attracts and motivates the customers to go for the product It is mostly useful for gathering the information of the customers and create the awareness about the new product or the new location for getting the products. Sweepstakes is a form of sales promotions that offers prizes based on a chance drawing of entrants' names (Duncan, 2004). Winners are determined purely by chance. Sweepstakes cannot require a proof of purchase as a condition for entry (Belch & Belch, 2008). Contest is a promotion whereby consumers compete for prizes or money on the basis of skill or ability. Winners are determined by judging the entries or ascertaining which entry comes closest to some predetermined criteria (Belch & Belch, 2008).

Bonus Pack: The bonus pack is getting additional quantity of the same product offered for the standard pack size purchased. The customers purchasing huge quantity than the regular size would be offered the bonus pack. This promotional activity would be used as the strategy for high sales and induce the customers to buy more quantity (Musibau, Choi & Oluyinka, 2014).

Free Trail: The free trail is also the sales promotional method that introduce to the new product in the market to the customers where they get to know about the product before purchasing it. Free trail strategy are much more popular for sales of software, computer programs, apps. These are the products that can be used for free for time being and required to be purchased later for further use. This would convince the customers to purchase the product for future use (Belch & Belch, 2008).

Consumer Purchase Intention

Consumer purchase intention refers to the subjective probability of buying behavior. This is formed by the subjective choice of consumers in the process of cognition of products through the stimulation of external conditions. Nena (2003) proposed that the purchase intention will directly affect the purchase behavior, which is the direct indicator of the purchase behavior of the customer. It is defined as whether the consumer is willing to understand the product or not, whether there is a purchase intention or not, combined with the characteristics of the social media, it selects the point strike link, the purchase, and the purchase of other platforms. Buy and will go to the physical store to purchase these 4 indicators to comprehensively measure the consumers' purchase intention (Wang, 2012). Therefore, the willingness of a customer to buy a certain product or a certain service is known as purchase intention. Kim and Kim

(2004) define purchase intention as the tendency of consumers with the identified aim where it is usually measured in terms of real purchasing. Moreover, Crosno, Freling and Skinner (2009) described that purchase intention refers to the possibility of purchasing a special brand in a product category during purchase. However, the implementation of the product's purchase intention depends on various factors such as customer willingness and interest to the product, imposed social pressure on the customer from others and a general sense of what is received. Purchase intention is the objective intention of a consumer toward a product, and the intention can be a crucial element for predicting the purchase-related behavior of consumers (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). Purchase intention can be defined as an individual's intention to purchase a specific product or brand after evaluation of the brand or product.

Purchase intention is the decision making process conducted by consumers before conducting purchase transaction over certain product needed by the consumers (Anoraga, 2000). Febryan (2010) stated that purchasing interest can be realized when the criteria consistent with the customers' want. Purchase intention often does not come in the mind sometimes becoming the customers' reason of not purchasing product or service they have often purchased. Purchase interest, according to Ferdinand (2006) can be identified through the following variables. The first is transactional interest, the tendency to purchase a product. The second is preferential interest, the interest representing an individual's behavior with primary preference to the product. The third is exploratory interest, the one representing an individual's behavior always searching for information on the product he/she prefers to support the positive characteristics of product.

Theoretical Framework

This research work is anchored on theory of reasoned action. The theory of reasoned action was formulated by Martin Fishbein and Icek Ajzen (1975 and 1980). The theory explains behavioral intentions, spanning prediction of attitude and prediction of behavior. TRA was developed to evaluate individual behavior by examining their attitudes, beliefs and behavioral intentions coupled with observed/expressed acts. Also, the theory suggest that most determinant of person's behavior is his/her behavioral intentions, which involves the negative or positive feeling leading to "perform or not to perform" that particular action.

TRA is generally anchored on three constructs: behavioral intentions, attitudes and subject norms. TRA suggests that a person's behavioral intentions depend on person's attitude about the behavior and subjective norms. This implies that if a person intend to do behavior then it is likely that the person's readiness to perform a given behavior, their subjective norms and their perceived behavioral control. Theory of reasoned action holds that only specific attitudes towards the behavior in question can be expected to predict that behavior. Similarly, in measuring attitudes towards behavior, there is need to measure people's subjective norms; there belief about how people they care about view the behavior in question. Knowledge of this beliefs, can determined the persons attitudes. However, the theory suggests that attitudes and norms are not weighted equally in predicting behavior; though, a weight is associated with each of this factor in predictive formula of the theory. In other word, if someone cares little for what others thinks, then the subjective norms in this case would carry little weight in predicting behavior. Mullin (2010) defines each of the three components of TRA as follows:

- ❖ **Attitudes:** The sum of beliefs about a particular behaviour weighted by evaluations of these consequences. That is, an individual may have a belief towards a particular act and at the same time weight the consequences.
- ❖ **Subjective Norms:** This look at the influence of people in one's social environment on his/her behavioural intentions, the beliefs of people weighted by importance one attributes to each of their opinions, will influence one's behavioural intentions. Hence, it is a combination of perceived expectations from relevant individuals or groups alongside the intentions to comply with this expectation.
- ❖ **Behavioural Intention:** This is the function of both attitudes toward behaviour and subjective norms to that particular behaviour, which has been found to predict actual behaviour. This implies that, one's attitudes toward an actions combined with the subjective norms about that action, each with their

weight, will lead to their intention to either take that action or not, which then lead to actual behaviour.

This theory is related to the study in that a person's attitude combined with subjective norms forms his/her behavioral intention. However, the theory states that attitudes and norms are not weighted equally in predicting behavior. Indeed, depending on the individual and situation, these factors might have very different effects on behavioral intentions. Therefore, a weight (consequences) is associated with each of the factors on predicting individual behaviors. Relating this theory to the work under study is in the prediction of individuals' intention to engage in a certain behavior at a specific time and place. This is the ability of soft drinks firms to use the various sales promotion tools to change the attitude and behavior of consumers to purchase their product at that particular time and place of promotions and makes sales because sale promotion deals with sales at a particular time and place.

Empirical Review

This section covers existing empirical evidence on the relationship between sales promotion and customer satisfaction. Ubeja (2014) carried a study on the effect of sales promotion mix on customer satisfaction with reference to shopping malls in Indore. The objectives of this study were to investigate the effects of sales promotion mix on customer satisfaction in shopping malls of Indore city and to study the variations in these factors across different demographic variables. The sample included 175 active mall shoppers. In this study, lucky and bumper offers, frequent and warranty offers, monetary and quantity benefit offers, gift and exchange offers and discount offers were employed as the explanatory variable while customer satisfaction was employed as the dependent variable. Factor analysis and ANOVA test were employed in analyzing the data. The study found that Indore customers consider spot movement offers and warranties of the product while purchasing the products in shopping malls. The study also found that monetary and quantity benefit offers, gift and exchange offers and discount offers have significant effect on customer satisfaction.

Jin-Woo, Yu-Jin and Woo-Choon (2013) investigated the effects of sales promotions on customer behavioral intentions at duty-free shops at Incheon International Airport. In this study, price, coupons, free gifts and points accumulation were employed as the independent variable while customer satisfaction, customer value, image and behavioral intention were employed as the dependent variable. Correlation analysis and structural equation modeling were applied in analyzing the data. Price and coupons were found as significant drivers of customer satisfaction, which was directly related to customer value, image, and behavioral intentions. Free gift and point accumulation were found to have insignificant effect on customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction had a positive influence on customer value, image and behavioral intentions. Customer value had a positive effect on behavioral intentions.

Weerathunga and Pathmini (2015) examined the impact of sales promotion on consumer's impulse buying behaviour in supermarkets in Anuradhapura City. Four (04) supermarkets located in Anuradhapura city were chosen as a sample and 106 consumers were selected using convenience and judgmental sampling techniques from these supermarkets. Price discount, Free samples, Buy-one Get-one free and Loyalty program was used as sales promotion tools to check its impact to the impulse buying behavior. Uni-variate, Bivariate and Multivariate analysis were employed in analyzing the data. The result of the study shows that sales promotion has significant impact on Consumers' impulse buying behaviour in supermarkets. Also, there is a significant impact of price discount, free sample, buy-one Get-one free and loyalty program on consumers' impulse buying behaviour. Results of Multiple Regression Analysis found that Loyalty program has the greatest significant impact on consumers' impulse buying behaviour than other sales promotional techniques.

Nwielaghi and Ogwo (2013) examined trade sales promotion strategies and marketing performance in the soft drink industries in Nigeria. With a survey research design, a regression model was formulated to incorporate eleven hypotheses of interests. Quantitative data were collected through a 5-point Likert-type scale questionnaire. A total of 234 copies of questionnaire were completed by senior promotion and sales executives of two major soft drink manufacturing firms and their accredited distributors in Nigeria. We adopted Pearson's 'r' and stepwise regression with its constituents-ANOVA and T-test to determine the

trade sales promotion activities that actually influence marketing performance activities in these firms. Two of the hypothesized trade sales promotion strategies were retained and adjudged relevant in determining marketing performance levels. The findings reveal that Trade promotion strategies affect marketing performance through the use of trade allowances and trade contests..

Pembi, Fudamu and Adamu (2017) examined the impact of sales promotional strategies on organizational performance in Nigeria in Flour Mills Maiduguri, Borno State Nigeria. The population of this study was carved out of the entire staff of the Flour Mills of Nigeria Maiduguri, Borno State branch cutting across the Top, Middle and lower level management. The study employed both the primary and secondary sources of data collection. Questionnaires were administered to twenty (20) staff using random sampling techniques. The data collected were subjected to descriptive statistics and regression analyses were. The result signifies that sales promotional strategies have positive and significant effects on organizational performance.

Amusat, Adejumo and Ajiboye (2013) investigated sales promotion as an antecedent of sales volume in selected manufacturing industry in Ibadan, south western, Nigeria. In this study, Coupon, bonus, free sample, premium and price promotion were employed as the explanatory variables while sales volume was employed as the dependent variable. The data generated were analyzed using regression analysis. Result shown that sales promotion dimensions such as bonus, coupons, free samples, price promotion and premiums were joint predictors of sales volume ($F(5, 74) = 2.261$; $R^2 = 0.13$; $P < .05$). The predictor variables jointly explained 13% of the variance of sales volume, while the remaining 87% could be due to the effect of extraneous variables such as advertising, publicity, pricing, brand name, product quality etc.

Adeniran, Egwuonwu and Egwuonwu (2016) investigated the impact of sales promotions on sales turnover in airlines industry in Nigeria. In this study, sales turnover was employed as the dependent variable while sales promotion incentives, none monetary sales promotional offer, off-line incentives and online offer were employed as the explanatory variables. Regression and t-test were employed in analyzing the data. The results show that sales promotions incentives significantly impacted sales turnover in the airlines industry; and air travellers prefer non-monetary sales promotional offers and off-line incentives to monetary and online offers.

Musibau, Choi and Oluyinka (2014) investigated the impact of sales promotion and product branding on company Performance: A case study of AIICO Insurance Nigerian PLC. In this study, repurchase patronage and productivity were employed as the dependent variable while sales promotion and product branding were employed as the independent variables. Chi-square statistical technique was employed in analyzing the data. Findings show that product branding and sales promotion affect organizational growth. This study findings show that there is a important impact on the effect of product brands and sales promotion on the development of Insurance industry in Nigeria and this effect cannot be underestimated.

Tandoh and Sarpong (2015) investigated the impact of sales promotions on the performance of automobile industries in Ghana with particular reference to PHC Motors (Accra-Ghana). In this study, market shares, returns and profit margin were employed as the dependent variable while Coupon, trade show, contest and sweepstakes, point of purchase display, premium, image difference and cultural receptiveness were employed as the independent variable. Percentages, bar and pie chart were used in analyzing the data. The research revealed that the impact of sales promotion on organizational performance in PHC is intense. Also, from the management perspective most of the respondents agree that sale promotion provides extra incentives to purchase as well as stimulating resellers demand and effectiveness.

Evinah and Boaz (2015) investigated the influence of integrated marketing communication and sales performance of commercial banks in Kenya. Sales performance was employed as the dependent variable while advertising, personal selling, sales promotion, public relations and direct marketing were employed as the independent variables. Correlation and Regression analysis were employed in analyzing the data. The study found that there was a positive relationship between independent variables (advertising, personal selling, sales promotion, public relations and direct marketing) and dependent variable (Sales Performance of Commercial Banks in Kenya).

Gap in Literature

The empirical literature reviewed revealed conflicting findings on the effect of sales promotion on consumer purchase intention. Similarly, majority of the scholarly work reviewed were foreign with only few local studies in soft drink sub-sector, hence a big knowledge gap in Nigeria. Despite the previous extensive research work, there is evident gap in knowledge in terms of the effect of sales promotion on consumer purchase intention in the soft drink sub-sector in South-East geo-political zone, Nigeria. This study will try to bridge this gap in knowledge.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a survey research design. This design was adopted because it interprets and synthesizes useful data for sound conclusion. The geographical location of the study was South-East Nigeria which comprises Anambra State, Enugu State, Ebony State, Imo State and Abia State. The capital territory and one satellite town in each of these states were selected for the study. Awka and Ekwulobia were selected in Anambra State, Owerri and Okigwe were selected in Imo State, Umuahia and Osioma were selected in Abia State, Enugu and Nsukka were selected in Enugu State while Abakiliki and Nkalagu were selected for Ebony State. Consumers of nine soft drinks namely Coke, Fanta, Sprite, Big Cola, 7up, La Casera, and Pepsi were selected for the study.

The study population for this research comprised of consumers of nine soft drinks namely Coke, Fanta, Sprite, Big Cola, 7up, La Casera, Nutri Milk, Viju Milk and Pepsi in South East Nigeria. Since the population of the study is not known, the statistical formula devised by Cochran (1963) was employed. Therefore, the sample size is approximately 384. Thereafter, the sample size was distributed equally among the states. The study used questionnaire as data collection instrument. Multiple regression analysis was conducted to test the hypotheses formulated exclusively for this study. Multiple regression analysis was conducted to assess the relative predictive power of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The regression model is presented in functional form as;

$$CPI = f(\text{PRD, CSS, COUP, BOP, FRT})$$

Where

CPI = Customer Purchase Intention

PRD = Price Discount

CSS = Contest and Sweepstakes

COUP = Coupon

BOP = Bonus Pack

FRT = Free Trail

$$CPI = \alpha + \beta_1\text{PRD} + \beta_2\text{CSS} + \beta_3\text{COUP} + \beta_4\text{BOP} + \beta_5\text{FRT} + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

Where:

Y = Dependent Variables

α = Constant Term

β = Beta Coefficients

β_1 to β_5 = Independent variables

ϵ = Error Term

RESULTS

Multiple regression analysis was employed to test the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

Table 1: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.784 ^a	.615	.592	4.159	2.771

a. Predictors: (Constant), Free Trail, Price Discount, Bonus pack, Contest and Sweepstakes, Coupon

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1	.784 ^a	.615	.592	4.159	2.771

a. Predictors: (Constant), Free Trail, Price Discount, Bonus pack, Contest and Sweepstakes, Coupon

b. Dependent Variable: Customer Purchase Intention

Source: SPSS Version 21.0

The model summary shows that R square, adjusted R square and Durbin-Watson statistics. The coefficient of determination (R^2) was employed to predict and evaluate the predictive accuracy of a structural model. It also shows the combined effects of the independent variables on the dependent variable. This explains the extent to which the variability of a factor can be caused or explained by their relationship with other factors. Table 1 indicates R Square and Adjusted R Square value of 61.5% and 59.2% respectively. This implies that 61.5% of the variations in the customer purchase intention are accounted by variations in free trail, price discount, bonus pack, contest and sweepstakes, and coupon. This indicates that sales promotional tools studied accounted for 61.5% variation in the customer purchase intention.

The Durbin-Watson statistics which measures the presence or otherwise of autocorrelation in the model shows that there is no autocorrelation in the model given the result of 2.771. This shows that that the variables in the model are not autocorrelated and therefore are reliable for predictions.

Table 2 ANOVA Result

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	216.918	5	43.384	2.508	.030 ^a
Residual	6191.521	358	17.295		
Total	6408.440	363			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Free Trail, Price Discount , Bonus pack, Contest and Sweepstakes , Coupon

b. Dependent Variable: Customer Purchase Intention

Source: SPSS Version 21.0

ANOVA enables to examine the main effect of independent variables to dependent variable. The effect size (F^2) is an additional measure that is used to assess the R^2 for all endogenous constructs to understand the significance of their impact. It also assesses the substantive influence of the predictor construct on the dependent variable. The F-statistics value of 2.508 with a probability value of 0.0030 in table 2 indicated that sales promotion proxied by free trail, price discount, bonus pack, contest and sweepstakes, and coupon has combined significant effect on customer purchase intention. This result showed that free trail, price discount, bonus pack, contest and sweepstakes, and coupon can collectively explain the variations in customer purchase intention of selected soft drink in South East Nigeria.

Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses formulated for the study were empirically tested using the coefficient of the regression analysis. In testing these hypotheses, the t value and probability value in table 3 were used and are presented below.

Table 3 Coefficient of the Regression Result

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	16.233	2.580		6.291	.000
	Price Discount	.008	.052	.008	3.147	.000
	Contest and Sweepstakes	.044	.054	.043	2.809	.000
	Coupon	.152	.054	.152	2.843	.001
	Bonus pack	.085	.055	.081	2.532	.004

Free Trail	.034	.069	.026	2.496	.003
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a. Dependent Variable: Customer Purchase Intention

Source: SPSS Version 21.0

Hypothesis One

Ho: Price discount does not have significant influence on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.

Price discount has a t value of 3.147 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that price discount have significant influence on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

Ho: Contest and sweepstakes does not have significant influence on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.

Contest and sweepstakes has a t value of 2.809 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that contest and sweepstakes have significant influence on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three

Ho: Coupon does not have significant influence on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.

Coupon has a t value of 2.843 and a probability value of 0.001 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that coupon has significant influence on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.

Hypothesis Four

Ho: Bonus packs does not have significant influence on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.

Bonus packs has a t value of 2.532 and a probability value of 0.004 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that bonus packs have significant influence on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.

Hypothesis Five

Ho: Free trail does not have significant influence on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.

Free trail has a t value of 2.496 and a probability value of 0.003 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that free trail have significant influence on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study investigated the influence of sales promotion on customer purchase intention of selected soft drinks in South East Nigeria. The data generated were subjected to statistical analysis and the following were ascertained. The study found that price discount has significant influence on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria. This indicates that when price discount are offered on soft drinks, it affects customers purchase intention. This agrees with the position of Yin and Huang (2014) that price discount is a very prevalent marketing strategy to attract consumers by providing an extra value or incentive and this encourages consumers to purchase the promoted products immediately. Similarly, Liao, Shen and Chu (2009) found that immediate price discount is an effective sales promotion strategy in influencing the purchasing behavior for both rational and non-rational consumers.

Contest and sweepstakes was found to have significant influence on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria. This agrees with the findings of Shahriar and Tahmores (2012) that sales promotion has a positive effect as a tool on customers' attention to purchase.

Coupon was found to have significant influence on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria. This agrees with the findings of Chen et al. (1998) that coupon has positive influence on

purchase intention. It also agrees with the position of Raghubir (2004) who found that an increase in face value of coupon influenced directly the purchase rates.

Bonus packs were found to have significant influence on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria. This agrees with the position of Musibau, Choi and Oluyinka (2014) that bonus pack is used as the strategy for high sales and induces the customers to buy more quantity. Similarly Ong et al. (1997) found that bonus packages, apart from provoking perceptions of greater value, they also produce greater purchase intentions for a product.

Free trial was found to have significant influence on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria. This agrees with the position of Belch and Belch (2008) that free trial convinces the customers to purchase the product for future use. Similarly, Alvarez and Casielles (2005) noted that free trial for a particular brand can also lead consumers to be willing to buy the product, even if they were not used to buy that brand. It also agrees with the position of Shimp (2003) that free sample can influence consumer buying behavior especially their intention to buy.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the influence of sales promotion on customer purchase intention of selected soft drinks in South East Nigeria. The study found that price discount, contest and sweepstakes, coupon, bonus pack and free trial have significant influence on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria. The study therefore concludes that sales promotion has significant influence on customer purchase intention of soft drinks in South East Nigeria. This work has proved that sales promotion tools covered in this study stimulate interest in consumers and consumers are bound to make purchase decision provided that they are offered with right price discount, contest and sweepstakes, coupon, bonus pack and free trial. Overall, sales promotion tools are playing an important role to stimulate customers towards buying any promoted product, and that will definitely increase dealers and retailers profit and market share.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommends the following:

1. Producers and distributors of soft drinks in South East Nigeria should occasionally use price discount in order to stimulate sales especially during off-peak periods.
2. Considering the keen nature of competition in the industry firms should be innovative in their contest and sweepstakes sales promotional strategy so that they can influence customers to their favour.
3. Also soft drinks manufacturing firms and their distributors should introduce appropriate platform that can publicize the various sales promotion programmes they offer to their clients particularly coupon in order to enhance customer purchase intention.
4. There is need for more innovative, dynamic and well-differentiated bonus pack by the company if they desire to maintain and increase the market share since bonus pack was found to have significant positive effect on customer purchase intention.
5. Manufacturers of soft drinks should provide free trial especially when they want to introduce new products as this will enhance customer purchase intention.

REFERENCES

- Adeniran, J. A., Egwuonwu, T. K., & Egwuonwu, C. O. K. (2016). The impact of sales promotions on sales turnover in airlines industry in Nigeria. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 2(3), 123 – 134.
- Aderemi, S. A. (2003). *Marketing principles and practice*. Mushin: Concept Publication Limited.
- Alvarez, B. A., & Casielles, R. V. (2005). Consumer evaluations of sales promotion: the effect on brand choice. *European Journal of Marketing*, 39(1), 54 – 70.

- Amusat, W.A., Adejumo, D.A., & Ajiboye, F. A. (2013). Sales promotion as an antecedent of sales volume: a study of selected manufacturing industry in Ibadan, south western, Nigeria. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary research in Business*, 4(11) 465 – 475
- Anoraga, P. (2000). *Manajemen bisnis*. Jakarta: PT. Rineka Cipta
- Belch, G.E., & Belch, M.A. (2008). *Advertising and promotion: An integrated marketing communications perspective* (8th ed.). New York, NY: McGraw-Hill Irwin.
- Chang, T., & Wildt, A.R. (1994). Price, product information, and purchase intention: An empirical study. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 22(1), 16-27.
- Crosno, J.I., Freling, T.H., & Skinner, S.J. (2009). Does brand social power mean market might? Exploring the influence of brand social power on brand evaluation, *Psychology and Marketing*, 26, 91–121.
- Devlin, J., Ennew, C., McKechnie, S., & Smith, A. (2007). A study of time limited sales promotions. *Journal of Product and Brand Management*, 16(4), 280 – 285.
- Duncan, T. (2004). *Principles of advertising & IMC*. (2nd ed.). New York, NY: McGraw-Hill Irwin.
- Evinah, M. M., & Boaz, N. (2015). Influence of integrated marketing communication and sales performance of commercial banks in Kenya. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publication*, 5(9) 1 – 20
- Ferdinand, A. (2006). *Metode Penelitian Manajemen*. Semarang. Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro Semarang.
- Fishbein, M., & Ajzen, I. (1975). *Belief, attitude, intention, and behavior: An introduction to theory and research*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.
- Hackeley, C. (2010). *Advertising and promotion: An integrated marketing communication approach*, 2nd edition. Great Britain: Cornwall.
- Jin-Woo, P., Yu-Jin, C., & Woo-Choon, M. (2013). Investigating the effects of sales promotions on customer behavioral intentions at duty-free shops: An Incheon International Airport case study. *Journal of Airport and Airline Management*, 3(1), 18 – 30.
- Kotler, P. (2009). *Marketing management* (11th ed.). New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2011). *Marketing management*, 14th edition. New Jersey, USA: Prentice Hall.
- Liao, S., Shen, Y., & Chu, C. (2009). The effects of sales promotion strategy, product appeal and consumer traits on reminder impulse buying behaviour. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 33(3), 274-284.
- Musibau, A. A., Choi, S. L., & Oluyinka, S. (2014). The impact of sales promotion and product branding on company Performance: A case study of AIICO Insurance Nigerian PLC. *Procedia: Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 129, 164 – 171.
- Nwielaghi, B. M. & Ogwo, E. (2013). Trade sales promotion strategies and marketing performance in the soft drink industries in Nigeria. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 5(4), 96 – 109.
- Obasan, K., & Soyobo, Y. (2012). Assessing the effectiveness of promotion as marketing management tool in the Nigerian Telecommunication Industry. *Journal of Emerging trends of Economics and Management Science*, 3(1), 1 - 6.
- Odunlade, A.R. (2009). Assessing the performance of sales promotion in sustaining farms product in Nigeria cities. *Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 3(5), 11 - 19.
- Ong, B.S., Ho, F.N., & Tripp, C. (1997). Consumer perceptions of bonus packs: an exploratory analysis. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 14(2), 102 – 112.
- Oyedapo, W.O., Akinlabi, B. H., & Sufian, J. B, (2012). The impact of sales promotion on organization effectiveness in Nigeria manufacturing industry. *Universal Journal of Marketing and Business Research*, 14, 128-131.
- Oyeniyi, O. (2011). Sales promotion and consumer loyalty: A study of sales Nigerian Telecommunication Industry. *Journal of competitiveness*, 3(2), 341 – 351. .

- Pembi, S., Fudamu, A. U., & Adamu, I. (2017). Impact of sales promotional strategies on organizational performance in Nigeria. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Management Sciences*, 5(4), 31 – 42.
- Raghubir, P., Inman, J. J., & Grande, H. (2004). *The three faces of consumer promotions*. *California Management Review*, 46(4), 23–42.
- Raney, A.A., Arpan, L.M., Pashupati, K., & Brill, D.A., 2003. At the movies, on the web: An investigation of the effects of entertaining and interactive web content onsite and brand evaluations. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 17(4), 38-53.
- Shahriar, A. C., & Tahmores, H. Y. (2012). Effect of sales promotion as a tool on customer attention to purchase: A case study of auto Maker Company. *African Journal of Business Management*, 6(5), 207 – 214.
- Shimp, T. A. (2000). *Advertising, promotion and supplemental aspects of integrated marketing communications* 5th edition. USA: Dryden Press.
- Shimp, T.A. (2003). *Advertising, promotion, and supplemental aspects of integrated marketing communications*, 6th ed.. USA: Thomson South-Western.
- Tandoh, I., & Sarpong, L. (2015). The impact of sales promotions on the performance of auto-mobile industries in Ghana: A case study of PHC Motors (Accra-Ghana). *European Journal of Business and Management* 7(11) 176 – 194.
- Ubeja, S. (2014). A study of sales promotion mix on customer satisfaction with reference to shopping malls in Indore. *Global Journal of Finance and Management*, 6(3), 245-252.
- Wang, X. (2012). The influence of advertising appeal and brand personality perception difference on consumer purchase intention research. *Management Journal*, 9(4), 555-561.
- Weerathunga A.K., & Pathmini M.G.S. (2015). Impact of sales promotion on consumer's impulse buying behaviour (IBB); study in supermarkets in Anuradhapura City. *International Research Symposium, Rajarata University of Sri Lanka*, 321 – 329.